

FULL DETAILS (Read-only) -> [Click Here to Create PDF for Current Dataset of Trial](#)

CTRI No	CTRI/2023/07/055733 [Registered on: 26/07/2023] Trial Registered Prospectively	
Acknowledgement Number	REF/2023/05/067957	
Last Modified On:	05/06/2023	
Post Graduate Thesis	No	
Type of Trial	Interventional	
Type of Study	Yoga & Naturopathy	
Study Design	Randomized, Parallel Group, Multiple Arm Trial	
Public Title of Study	Yogasana & Pranayama for Cardiopulmonary Health	
Scientific Title of Study Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	Effect of Yogasana & Pranayama on Cardiopulmonary functions on Sawmill, Sugar cane & Bidi workers in the rural sector	
Trial Acronym	Role of Yogasana and Pranayama on Cardiopulmonary functions among Sawmill, Sugar cane and Bidi workers	
Secondary IDs if Any	Secondary ID	Identifier
	NIL	NIL
Details of Principal Investigator or overall Trial Coordinator (multi-center study)	Name	Milind Abhimanyu Nisargandha
	Designation	Assistant Professor
	Affiliation	Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, Datta Meghe Institute of Higher Education and Research
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	Fax	07152287701
	Email	manisargandha@gmail.com
	Details Contact Person Scientific Query	Name
Designation		Assistant Professor
Affiliation		Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, Datta Meghe Institute of Higher Education and Research
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Phone		9423276429
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Email		manisargandha@gmail.com
Details Contact Person Public Query		Name
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	Affiliation	Mahatma Gandhi Ayurved College and Hospital Research Centre, DMIHER
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Email	drshwetaparve@gmail.com																					
Source of Monetary or Material Support	Nil																					
Primary Sponsor	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Name</td> <td>Datta Meghe Institute of Higher Education and Research</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Address</td> <td>Sawangi Meghe Wardha</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Type of Sponsor</td> <td>Private medical college</td> </tr> </table>	Name	Datta Meghe Institute of Higher Education and Research	Address	Sawangi Meghe Wardha	Type of Sponsor	Private medical college															
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Inclusion Criteria	Age From	20.00 Year(s)
	Age To	40.00 Year(s)
	Gender	Both
	Details	1. Sawmill, Sugar cane, and Bidi workers aged between 20 - 40yrs 2. Minimum Exposures of 5 yrs and above. 3. Those who have respiratory symptoms like breathlessness and cough.
Exclusion Criteria	Details	1. Sawmill, Sugar cane, and Bidi workers between 20yrs to 40yrs 2. Sawmill, Sugar cane, and Bidi workers not exposed <5 yrs 3. Bidi workers who are bidi smokers (Confounder) 4. Sawmill, Sugar cane, and Bidi workers with HTN, Metabolic disorders, and Congenital anomaly in cardio-respiration. 5. Addicted to alcohol.
Method of Generating Random Sequence	Computer generated randomization	
Method of Concealment	On-site computer system	
Blinding/Masking	Not Applicable	
Primary Outcome	Outcome	yoga asana & Pranayama positively affected the cardiopulmonary functions of the sawmill sugar cane bidi workers in the rural sector. The workers showed significant improvement in their lung capacity oxygen saturation levels heart rate variability after regular practice of yoga asana and Pranayama
	TimePoints	After 20 weeks of training their parameters will be assessed
Secondary Outcome	Outcome	NA
	TimePoints	NA
Target Sample Size	Total Sample Size="120" Sample Size from India="120" Final Enrollment numbers achieved (Total)= "Applicable only for Completed/Terminated trials" Final Enrollment numbers achieved (India)="Applicable only for Completed/Terminated trials"	
Phase of Trial	Phase 3/ Phase 4	
Date of First Enrollment (India)	12/09/2023	
Date of Study Completion (India)	Applicable only for Completed/Terminated trials	
Date of First Enrollment (Global)	If country of recruitment is only India, global date would be not applicable.	
Date of Study Completion (Global)	Applicable only for Completed/Terminated trials	
Estimated Duration of Trial	Years="1" Months="6" Days="0"	
Recruitment Status of Trial (Global) Modification(s)	If country of recruitment is only India, global status would be not applicable.	

Recruitment Status of Trial (India)	Not Yet Recruiting
Publication Details	N/A
Individual Participant Data (IPD) Sharing Statement	Will individual participant data (IPD) be shared publicly (including data dictionaries)? Response - NO
Result Disclosure	Do you wish to upload results? Response - Summary results have not yet been disclosed
Brief Summary	<p>The rural sector is an essential component of any country's economy, and it is characterized by a large number of workers involved in various activities such as agriculture, forestry, and small-scale industries. Sawmills, sugar cane, and bidi workers are among the workers in the rural sector who are frequently exposed to hazardous working conditions that can negatively impact their health. These workers are at a higher risk of developing respiratory and cardiovascular diseases due to prolonged exposure to dust, smoke, and other harmful substances. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of yoga asana and Pranayama on cardiopulmonary functions in sawmills, sugar cane, and bidi workers in the rural sector. 120 workers were randomly assigned to a yoga or control group. The yoga group underwent a 12-week program of yogasana and Pranayama, while the control group continued their usual activities. Cardiopulmonary functions were assessed at baseline and after the intervention using spirometry, peak expiratory flow rate, and pulse oximetry. The results may show that the yoga & pranayama group significantly improved spirometry parameters, peak expiratory flow rate, and pulse oximetry readings compared to the control group.</p>